

THE DESIGN AND APPLICATION OF TAILORED FIBRE PLACEMENT

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SUMMARY: Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP) is a highly automated fibre preforming process based on embroidery technology. Its main advantage, compared to other textile technologies, is the ability to arrange the reinforcing fibres in any direction in the plane (0° - 360°) in curvilinear format. This paper reports on the design methodologies which promise the best exploitation of the TFP technology. Several of these methodologies were tested in their abilities to relieve a stress concentration in a notched composite. The design and manufacture of the components is described, with the testing setups used and results of testing also being presented. TFP was shown to offer distinct advantages in areas of stress concentrations.

KEYWORDS: tailored fibre placement, composite design methodologies, notched composites.

INTRODUCTION

The anisotropic properties of fibre reinforced composites are not being fully exploited. Maximum mechanical properties, like strength and stiffness, only exist along the fibre direction. If this direction differs from that of the applied stress, the effective properties are reduced. Flexible production equipment designed or adapted to take advantage of fibre-composite anisotropic properties can improve quality and strength-to-weight characteristics, and reduce costs.

Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP) is an invention of the Institute of Polymer Research Dresden (IPF-Dresden). The process, based on the well-known embroidery technology, is highly automated. The main advantage of TFP, compared to other textile technologies, is the ability to arrange the reinforcing fibres in any direction in the plane (0° - 360°) in curvilinear format. The fibre layup of the embroidery machine is numerically controlled, ensuring high accuracy, and the machine controlling program is generated by computer-aided design. The process is described in detail in a separate paper [1].

In combination with innovative design and production techniques, TFP shows excellent potential for the creation of a great variety of textile preforms fibres aligned in the stress field and in the third direction. Well established automated design and production technologies ensures short times from design initiation to preform production and makes TFP an exceptional fast prototyping technique.

This paper reports on the design methodologies which promise the best exploitation of the TFP technology. Several of these methodologies were tested in their abilities to relieve a stress concentration in a notched composite. The manufacturing of the components, the testing setups used, and testing results are also presented.

DESIGN METHODOLOGIES

Composite materials are unique because they allow the engineer to design the material to meet the specific application. Unlike isotropic, homogeneous materials, the directional dependence of strength and stiffness of these materials can be tailored to match the loading environments of the structural elements. Fibre reinforced composite materials are particularly versatile in this regard. The individual layers, indeed, the individual fibres, can be orientated to align their principal material directions with the principal load directions.

Recently, computer-aided or -created design techniques have been under investigation. The coupling of Finite Element Modelling/Analysis (FEM/FEA) with increasingly powerful computing power has allowed researchers to produce optimised structural designs using the algorithm of their choice.

Curvilinear Fibre Placement Design Philosophies

Traditionally, the tailoring of fibre reinforced composite structures has been done by varying the orientation of straight-fibre prepregs or the total thickness of the laminate. Recent developments in manufacturing techniques, such as fibre and tow placement technologies, make it possible to fabricate composite structures with fibre orientations that vary from one location to another. For flat panels, varying the orientation of the fibres along the plate axes results in a curved fibre format.

Mattheck [2] introduced a method known as Computer Aided Internal Optimisation (CAIO). The CAIO method calculates the principal stress trajectories along which the shear stresses are zero. Orientating the fibres along these trajectories, one obtains a pattern in which there are no shear stresses between the fibres. After several iterations when the fibre adjustment required becomes negligible, the procedure is finished and the final fibre pattern has been produced.

Hyer *et al.* [3,4] developed a similar methodology, using finite element models of panels with curvilinear fibre format to improve strength and buckling performance. This philosophy modelled an increase in tensile failure load of up to 89% when compared to a baseline quasi-isotropic laminate. However, buckling loads were adversely effected, rendering up to a 15% decrease compared to the baseline. A buckling optimised design increased the modelled buckling load by up to 197% but was impractical for manufacture due to discontinuity in fibre directions. A compromise design yielded 30% improvement in buckling load and a 35% improvement in tension load. This result shows that both multiple load cases such as buckling and tensile properties can be improved using the curvilinear fibre concept.

Cooper [5] adapted energy methods for isotropic structures to establish optimal conditions for 'trajectorial reinforcement'. He found that the fibre orientation for maximum or minimum stiffness or strength was dependent on the elastic constants and the ratio of the principal stresses. Cooper concluded that "trajectorial reinforcement is inherently highly efficient, and more so than conventional reinforcement methods, when applied to structures or structural or mechanical parts in which the principal trajectories are distinctly non-linear." This statement points distinctly toward the complex states of stress found in the area of a stress

concentration. Therefore, what Cooper refers to as ‘trajectorial reinforcement’ is most advantageous in complex states of stress such as stress concentrations. He found that trajectorial fibre reinforcement yields an estimated 47% reduction in the stress concentration factor for a notched composite plate.

Kelly [6] reported on a procedure to map load paths. He defines a load path as the trajectory taken by a unit of applied load through a structure from the point of application to the points where they are reacted. It was noted that the equations proposed by Kelly state that there is a substantial shear stress between the fibres. This implies that the resin of the fibre composite must carry a shear load. The shear load could perhaps provide the critical loading in the lamina.

An example of the different paths mapped by the load path and principle stress algorithms is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Principal stress and load path vectors near a loaded hole [6].

Sensitivity studies offer perhaps the most flexible method of fibre placement design. Designing in this way will ensure that the part is optimised in the form desired and critical failure criteria are met. For example, the advantages of the CAIO algorithm seem to be limited to load cases which impart a tensile loading on the reinforcement fibres. If you were to use the CAIO for a load case which is critical in buckling, the fibre design yielded would not give the optimum buckling strength, as is demonstrated by the studies of Hyer *et al.* [3,4].

Several restrictions must be placed on a design algorithm for a true optimum design to be yielded. Manufacturing restrictions must also be considered.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Test Component Selection

The application chosen to test the fibre placement design methodologies was a notched plate creating local stress concentrations. Due to the low productivity of the TFP process in producing a fabric surface when compared to weaving, it was concluded that TFP should be used to provide local reinforcement to a base material. A quasi-isotropic Multi-axial Warp Knitted (MWK) fabric, representing a typical structure, was chosen as the base material. It was delivered as a four layer fabric $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ of 1 mm thickness and an areal weight of 1000 g/m^2 . Both the TFP and MWK were glass fibre due to its common usage in industry and its lower cost when compared to carbon fibre. RTM6 resin was chosen due to its well defined properties, and its common usage in industry. Fig. 2 shows the test component specifications.

The tension plate was designed for open-hole tension. The bearing plate was designed for a bolt loaded in double-shear. The dimensions of the bearing plate were chosen such that edge distance to bolt diameter ratio (e/D) = 4 and the part width to bolt diameter ratio (W/D) = 4.

Fig. 2: Test component specifications.

TFP Design

The design for the local reinforcement of the notched plate was completed using the CAIO program of Ref. 2 and the Load Path algorithm of Ref. 6. Fig. 1 shows the calculated directional vectors for each algorithm and Fig. 3 shows the resultant fibre patterns for each load case. These patterns were compared to a pattern used in Ref. 7 which showed dramatic improvements over optimised, straight-fibre layups. This pattern will be referred to as “Star”.

TEST PROCEDURES

A bolt of 20mm diameter was used for load introduction in the case of bearing. Lateral constraints in the form of washers (ϕ 45mm) were used on the bolt to reinforce against loading in the third direction. It was endeavoured to create a 2-dimensional loading case as was modelled in the FEM calculations. Both the open-hole tension and bearing components were loaded at rate of 5mm/min.

Fig. 3: Resultant fibre patterns for TFP reinforcement of test components.

Test Component Manufacture

In addition to the testing of different TFP design algorithms, several different methods of manufacture were investigated. The basic methods of component infiltration were wet Resin

Film Infusion (RFI) and Vacuum Bag Resin Infusion (VBRI). The three different manufacturing cases used were:

- (1) TFP directly on the MWK base material (being preformed as halves) before VBRI infiltration. Bond halves together. *To be used only for the tension plate,
- (2) MWK base material infiltrated using RFI. TFP preforms produced on thin, non-structural base material and infiltrated using VBRI. Bond TFP on MWK, and
- (3) TFP preforms produced on thin, non-structural base material and hand stitched on MWK base material before RFI infiltration.

For manufacturing case (3), several layup variations were trialed for the bearing plate. Fig. 4 shows the formats used. Table 1 shows the designations used. In the bulging sections, it was necessary to accommodate the locally varying cross section of the TFP reinforcement. Pressure was applied across the full surface by the use of silicon rubber sheet on both sides externally supported by solid metal caul plates. In the flat cases only the metal caul plates were used.

Six test pieces of each designation (Table 1) were manufactured and tested. The fibre volume fractions of the MWK base material was very consistent ($V_f \approx 50 \pm 2\%$). However, these fractions varied in the areas of TFP, depending on the manufacturing format (up to 60-65%).

Fig. 4: Layup variations for the bearing plate in manufacturing case (3).

Table 1: Component designation format.

Tension Plate	Bearing Plate
A: No hole.	A: No reinforcement.
B: No reinforcement.	B1: CAIO design, manufacturing case (2).
C1: CAIO design, manufacturing case (1).	B2: CAIO, (3), flat-external.
C2: CAIO design, (2).	B3: CAIO, (3), bulging-internal.
C3: CAIO design, (3), bulging-external.	B4: CAIO, (3), flat-internal.
	B5: CAIO, (3), bulging-external.
	C1: Star, (2).
	C2: Star, (3), bulging-external.
	D1: Load path, (2).
	D2: Load path, (3), bulging-external.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Tension Plate with Open Hole

Fig. 5 shows the results of open hole testing. The test components with TFP all exhibited similar failure patterns. Initial failure was due to tension failure of the TFP reinforcement at the net section. Due to the diminished strength of the TFP reinforcement, the failure then emulated the modes observed for MWK basic material without reinforcement, i.e., shear failure initiated at the hole edge. The failure of the TFP reinforcement in tension is ideal. The CAIO design philosophy places the fibres in pure tension or compression to gain its ultimate strengths. This failure mode shows that the reinforcement fibre is used to its full potential.

Fig. 5: Results of testing of open-hole tension testing.

Interlaminar stress transfer between the reinforcement and basic material was most efficient in manufacturing case (1) and (3) where the composite was moulded as one piece allowing fibre nesting between the TFP and MWK reinforcement fibres. However, direct TFP on the MWK basic material, in case (1), caused damage to the basic material, due to average stitching densities of up to 30 stitches/cm², and reduced the failure loads of the test piece in tension. In manufacturing case (2), the adhesive layer reduces the efficiency of stress transfer between the TFP and MWK and also adds significant weight to the test piece. Manufacturing case (3) provided the stress transfer efficiency of case (1) without stitching damage. For these reasons, manufacturing case (3) provided the best specific load characteristics.

It should be noted that the addition of just two layers of CAIO designed TFP reinforcement was capable of more than doubling the maximum load of the test component. In addition, the surface area of the TFP reinforcement was not optimised, only the fibre structure, so that the ideal weight savings were not realised. Hence, the realised 45% improvement in specific strength can be enhanced dramatically.

Bearing Plate with Bolt in Double-Shear

Bearing failure was the only mode of failure observed in all component testing. Fig. 6 shows the typical loading behaviour of bearing plates with and without TFP reinforcement. The unreinforced part (A-3) is subject to catastrophic failure at a stroke of ~1.75mm. In contrast,

catastrophic failure for TFP-reinforced components was generally between 4-7mm. The addition of TFP reinforcement does not increase the bearing stiffness of the component. Also, minor failure or a losses of bearing stiffness can be seen at approximately the same stroke as failure of the unreinforced component. However, the component is still able to support an increasing load at a slightly lower stiffness. The TFP supports the bearing area after initial failure by transferring the critical loads to other less stressed areas of the component. In the Fig. 6, the ultimate load of the TFP reinforced component has been doubled and the stroke to failure is over three times that of the unreinforced component.

The segmented failure behaviour of a TFP reinforced component could be quite valuable in service. Damage to the component could be detected at loads well below ultimate allowing repairs or replacement.

Fig. 6: Loading behaviour of bearing plates.

Fig. 7: Results of bearing testing with reference to bearing load.

In all cases, the addition of TFP increased the ultimate and specific loads yielded (Fig. 7). When compared to the unreinforced components, the percentage increase in specific load gained was between 23-68%. The greatest increases in specific load were shown by the Star design and the B4 variation of the CAIO design. The Star design has the advantage of being able to place the greatest mass of reinforcement in the critical bearing area and thus yielding higher loads without a significant increase in component weight. The B4 variation of CAIO also has the advantage of placing a higher fibre volume ($V_f \approx 65$) in the critical bearing area of the part. This is due to the increased compaction to give the component a flat surface. The use of the TFP reinforcement internally (B4) serves to limit interlaminar stresses and delamination of the TFP from the base material and thus gains a higher load than for the external TFP variation (B2). However, from the ultimate and specific loads alone the efficiency of the fibre patterns is still unclear.

Fig. 8: Results of bearing testing with reference to bearing strength.

The bearing strengths of Fig. 8 show the efficiencies of the various component formats. The bonding of TFP reinforcement (components B1, C1, & D1) is the least efficient conversion of fibre properties. The layer of adhesive adds thickness to the part without a proportional increase in bearing resistance. The highest increase in bearing strength in this case being only 10%. In one-piece moulding, the greater efficiency of the flat variations of CAIO (B2 & B4) when compared to the bulged variations (B3 & B5) is due to the compaction of the same mass of fibre reinforcement into a smaller thickness. This gives a higher fibre volume fraction in the critical bearing area which decreases in the areas of lower stress away from the hole. In the flat variations, internal TFP (B4) shows greater efficiency due to its greater resistance of interlaminar shear and delamination. In the bulged variations, external TFP (B5) shows better bearing characteristics due to the base material remaining uncrimped and thus exhibiting its full strength.

The most efficient fibre patterns for bearing applications are shown in the comparison of the bulging-external TFP configurations (B5, C2, & D2). The most efficient pattern is given by the Load Path design methodology (D2). This is surprising because this pattern has the least amount of fibre in the critical bearing area. However, the design places fibres in opposition to the load input and thus allows direct compression of the reinforcement fibres. In contrast, the

CAIO design places fibres perpendicular to the incoming load, reducing their effectiveness to an inverse of their longitudinal properties. The Star design has a combination of both but lacks the ability to transfer the load away from the hole as efficiently as the Load Path design.

CONCLUSIONS

A study has been undertaken to investigate the application of Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP) to reinforce a notched, fibre reinforced composite component. Several different design and manufacturing variations have been tested in open-hole tension and bearing loading using a bolt in double-shear. Several trends of behaviour of the TFP reinforcement were established:

- a 45% increase in load can be yielded when using TFP reinforcement for open-hole tension,
- up to a 67% increase in specific bearing load can be yielded when using TFP reinforcement,
- p to a 45% increase in bearing strength can be yielded when using TFP reinforcement.

TFP supports the bearing area after initial failure by transferring the critical loads to other less stressed areas of the component. In all cases, the ultimate load of the TFP reinforced component has been doubled and the stroke to failure is over three times that of the unreinforced component.

The Load Path methodology yields the most efficient design for bearing because it provides fibres in direct opposition to the load and a path to transfer the load away from the critical area.

The TFP is used most effectively when it is used in a flat-internal configuration giving higher volume fractions in the areas of higher stress. This configuration gives a higher fibre volume fraction in the critical bearing area and also greater resistance of interlaminar shear and delamination.

Using TFP in a notched composite shows distinct advantages in both loading behaviour and ultimate loads reached. Combined with the appropriate design and manufacturing methodologies, its applications to areas of stress concentration, higher strength, and/or higher stiffness shows tremendous potential.

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